

Devyāmata, vāstudevābhīdhānāṣṭasatimatipāṭalaḥ, edition.

N f80r, line 3; M f47v, line 1.

At M, the folio that carries 77.7a – 78.10 is misplaced in the stack. W, in copying M, maintains this disordered account. I have not been able to locate 77.7a – 78.10 in W.

- 78.1 abhīdhānaviśeṣeṇa jñeyā brahmādayaḥ surāḥ
vāstumadhye sthito brahmā caturvaktro jagatpatiḥ
- 78.2 haro lokeśvaraḥ svīgaḥ parjanya meghanāthakaḥ
jayantaḥ kāśyapo jñeyo mahendras tu sureśvaraḥ
- 78.3 ādityo bhāskaro devo dharmāḥ satyaḥ prakīrtitaḥ
bhṛṣo hi kāmadevaḥ syād antarīkṣas tathāmbaraḥ
- 78.4 agnir hutāśano jñeyaḥ pūṣā mātṛgaṇaḥ smṛtaḥ
yamo vai ca svato jñeyo gandharvo nāradaḥ smṛtaḥ
- 78.5 nirṛtir bhṛṅgarājaḥ syāt mṛgo hy adharma ucyaṭe
pitaraḥ pitṛdevāḥ syuḥ pitṛlokanivāsinaḥ
- 78.6 nandir dvauvārikaḥ proktaḥ sugrīvo hi manuḥ smṛtaḥ
garutmān puṣpadantaḥ syād varuṇaḥ syād apāmpatiḥ
- 78.7 rāhus tathāsuro jñeyaḥ śoṣas tu śaniś caro grahaḥ
pāpayakṣmā kṣayo jñeyo rogo vāyuḥ prakīrtitaḥ

Ω = NM(→W)

- 1b brahmādayaḥ] em.; brahmādaya N; brahmadaya M 1d catur] em.; catu NM
- 2a lokeśvaraḥ] em.; lokesvara N; lokeśvaraṃ M 2b nāthakaḥ] N; nayakaḥ M
- 2c jayantaḥ] M; jayanta N • kāśyapo] N; kāśyayo M 2d sureśvaraḥ] M; svareśvaraḥ N
- 3a devo] N; devau M 3b dharmāḥ] N; dharma M • satyaḥ] N; satya M
- prakīrtitaḥ] em.; prakīrtitam NM 3c devaḥ] N; deva M 4a agnir] N; agni M
- 4b gaṇaḥ] N; gaṇa M 4d nāradaḥ] N; nārada M 5a nirṛtir] em.; niriti N; naitiriti M
- bhṛṅgarājaḥ] em.; bhṛṅgarāja N; dharmarāja M • syāt] N; syā M 5b mṛgo] em.; mṛṣo NM
- 5c devāḥ] N; devaḥ M • syuḥ] N; syu M 6a nandir] em.; nandi NM
- proktaḥ] N; prokta M 6b manuḥ] N; manu M 6c garutmān] N; garutmā M
- 6d varuṇaḥ] em.; varuṇa NM • patīḥ] N; patti M
- 7a jñeyaḥ] N; jñeyāḥ M 7c jñeyo] N; jñeyoḥ M
- 7d vāyuḥ] N; vāyu M • prakīrtitaḥ] M; prakīrtit[[ā]]ḥ N

78.8 nāgo hi vāsukir mukhyo viśvakarmā prakīrtitaḥ
bhalvāṣaś candramā jñeyaḥ somaḥ kubera ucyaṭe

78.9 anantaś carakaḥ proktaḥ aditiḥ śrīr udāhṛtā
śarvas tu ditir ity uktaḥ śūlapāṇir vṛṣadhvajāḥ

78.10 śailo vai himavān āpo hy āpavatsa umā smṛtā
ādityo hy āryamā proktā sāvitṛī vedamātrkaḥ

M f48r; W 52r, line 2

78.11 savitā ca smṛtā gaṅgā vivasvā ‡ ‡ akaḥ smṛtaḥ
indro harijayaś cokto vajra indrajayaḥ smṛtaḥ

N f80v

78.12 halāyudhaḥ smṛto mitro rudro jñeyo maheśvaraḥ
rājayaḥsmā guho jñeyo meruś ca pṛthivīdharāḥ

78.13 catvāriṃśat tathā pañca vāstudehe surāḥ smṛtāḥ
devatānusaṛāś cānyāś catasro vāstuno bahiḥ

78.14 īśānyādiṣu koṇeṣu carakyā saṃvyavasthitāḥ
vāstudehe samākhyātā vāstudevā yathāsthitāḥ

78.15 sirādimarmabhedam tu procyate śṛṇu sāmpratam

iti vāstudevābhīdhānāṣṭasatapatimapaṭalaḥ

Ω = NM(→W)

N is illegible at 13cd and 14ab

8a hi vāsukir] N; hi tyāsuki M 8b karmā] N; karma M 8c jñeyaḥ] N; jñeya M
8d somaḥ] N; soma M 9b aditiḥ] N; aditi M • udāhṛtā] N; udāhṛtāḥ M
9c ditir ity uktaḥ] em.; ditirityaktaḥ N; ditiristuktā M 9d pāṇir] em.; pāṇir N; pāṇi M
10b āpavatsa] em.; āpavatsā NM • smṛtā] N; smṛtāḥ M 10d sāvitṛī] em.; sāvitṛ NM
11a smṛtā] M; [**] N • gaṅgā] N; gaṅga M 11b ‡ ‡ akaḥ: hyaktakaḥ N; hyāttakaḥ M
11d jayaḥ] N; [[ya]]yaḥ M 12c rājayaḥsmā] em.; rājayaḥsmo M; [****] N
13a catvāriṃśat] em.; catvāriśa N; vāstumadhye M • tathā pañca] N; prayatneñca M
13b surāḥ smṛtāḥ] em.; surāḥsmṛtāḥ M; [****] N
13c devatānusaṛāś] conj.; devatānusaṛoś M 13d vāstuno bahiḥ] em.; vānobahi M
15a sirādi] em.; śirādi N; sirāsi M after 15 iti vāstudevābhīdhānāṣṭasatapatimapaṭalaḥ] em.;
itivāstudevābhīdhānapaṭalaḥ N; itidevyāmatevāstudevābhīdhānāṣṭasatapatimapaṭalaḥ M